

Original article

Beyond the trees. Benefits of a participatory-led renaturalisation in a marginalised neighbourhood

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ABSTRACT

Urban greening is often unequally distributed, and marginalised neighbourhoods are frequently excluded from top-down reforestation strategies, while the green areas they do have are of low ecological and aesthetic quality. In such environments, bottom-up greening strategies may better match local needs and improve stewardship and appropriation of newly allocated areas. To examine this possibility, we designed and implemented a neighbourhood-led renaturalisation project in Las Palmeras, Córdoba, Spain, based on a participatory action research framework and participatory greening process. We applied a mixed-methods, quasi-experimental design to assess ecological, social, and health and well-being outcomes through baseline (2023) and follow-up (2025) surveys in the intervention area and two comparison neighbourhoods. Additionally, we conducted a census of tree planting and survival and held focus groups with core participants. Adjusted models indicated improvements in nature-relatedness, outdoor time in natural settings, exercise in green areas, awareness of nature during activities, and neighbourhood image in the intervention area relative to the comparison areas. In contrast, population-level mental health indicators (WHO-5, K6, self-rated health and life satisfaction) did not show significant changes over the two-year period. Focus groups indicated increases in neighbourhood pride, social ties, and sense of ownership among participants. In contrast, health and well-being gains arising from ecosystem services such as cooling, shade, and biodiversity are likely to take several years to emerge as trees mature. Whereas social benefits such as participation, achievement, and belonging may arise during the process, bottom-up approaches encourage their achievement. Community-led greening in underserved areas should therefore receive political support as a pathway to implement immediate social benefits and future ecological co-benefits.

1. Introduction

Urban areas continue to experience an uneven distribution of accessible green spaces, particularly in neighbourhoods shaped by long-term socio-economic disadvantages (Kabisch et al., 2016; Rocha et al., 2024). In many cities, urban development has prioritised grey infrastructure over natural elements, resulting in reduced vegetation, loss of ecological function, and increased environmental stress. Limited green space has been associated with the urban heat island effect, poor air quality, and reduced biodiversity. These conditions are particularly concerning in the context of climate change, as many cities face higher temperatures and more frequent extreme weather events (Gill et al., 2007; Wolch et al., 2014a). Vulnerable populations, including residents with lower incomes, children, and older adults, are more likely to live in neighbourhoods with few or poorly maintained green areas, a pattern documented across many cities, particularly in Europe and North

America. Such conditions reflect broader environmental and spatial inequalities (Anguelovski et al., 2019; Kabisch et al., 2016).

Research has associated limited access to vegetation with increased rates of respiratory illness, cardiovascular disease, and mental health difficulties (Kabisch et al., 2017; World Health Organization, 2016, 2023). Different studies link contact with nature to better mental well-being, reduced stress, increased physical activity, and social cohesion (Barragan-Jason et al., 2023; Cardinali et al., 2024; Cruz-Piedrahita et al., 2022; Remme et al., 2021). Urban green spaces may also enable informal social interaction and strengthen a sense of belonging among residents (Hartig et al., 2014; van den Berg et al., 2015). Where such spaces are absent or in poor condition, these benefits are harder to obtain, particularly in already marginalised areas (Rigolon and Németh., 2020; Wolch et al., 2014b). Evidence suggests that even modest contact with vegetation can support positive psychological outcomes and a stronger connection to place (World Health Organization, 2016). Yet

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many residents of disadvantaged urban neighbourhoods have limited access to these experiences (Dadvand et al., 2016). Moreover, socio-spatial segregation can undermine the condition of the few green spaces that disadvantaged neighbourhoods do have. A wide body of evidence shows that damage to public goods, for example, malicious damage, and vandalism of fixtures and vegetation, is more common in poorer areas, driven by weaker informal social control, legitimacy gaps with authorities, and guardianship deficits (Ceccato and Haining, 2005; Dede et al., 2025; Keizer et al., 2008). The uneven distribution of quality green infrastructure raises important concerns for urban sustainability, public health, and spatial justice (Anguelovski et al., 2018). In this context, participatory-led urban renaturalisation offers a potential way to reintroduce nature into cities and to address historical inequalities in access to green space.

The literature indicates a double penalty for socio-spatially segregated, low-income neighbourhoods: fewer green spaces to begin with, and worse conditions in the existing spaces due to higher exposure to vandalism and damage, especially where maintenance is irregular, and community ownership is weak (Anguelovski et al., 2019; Keizer et al., 2008). This underscores that renaturalisation in such contexts is not only a question of adding vegetation to increase ecosystem services such as health reduction, but of governance, design, maintenance, and stewardship to interrupt disorder–decline feedbacks and secure equitable benefits (Buijs et al., 2016; Frantzeskaki and Tilie, 2014; Hansen et al., 2023). Urban renaturalisation interventions are increasingly common in cities, seeking to restore or increase ecological presence within urban environments. These projects may vary in scope and form but often involve the creation or rehabilitation of green areas, the planting of trees or native vegetation, and the integration of nature-based elements into existing infrastructure (Hansen et al., 2023). They aim to contribute to environmental improvements, but their outcomes depend in part on how they are planned and implemented.

Governance approaches shape how renaturalisation takes place. Top-down strategies are typically led by public institutions or planning departments and are often informed by environmental regulations, development frameworks, or climate adaptation plans. These approaches may offer technical expertise and coordination capacity, but are not always responsive to the specific needs or practices of local communities. Often, they have not reached the neighbourhoods most affected by environmental and spatial inequalities (Frantzeskaki, 2019; Hansen et al., 2019). In contrast, bottom-up initiatives often arise from community groups, local associations, or non-governmental organisations. These approaches tend to reflect local priorities and experiences and may encourage more inclusive forms of engagement; however, such projects may encounter difficulties due to limited resources, fragmented coordination, or lack of institutional recognition (Buijs et al., 2019). As a result, there is increasing interest in hybrid models that combine formal institutional capacity and resources with local participation. These arrangements may support the co-production of green infrastructure by aligning technical, financial, and administrative tools with community knowledge and priorities (Dorst et al., 2022).

However, there is still limited empirical evidence on how participatory renaturalisation unfolds in highly marginalised European neighbourhoods, particularly when implemented through governance arrangements that combine institutional actors and local residents. There is also little research that simultaneously examines ecological outcomes (such as tree survival and damage or vandalism) alongside social and health-related changes in these contexts. This study presents the outcomes of a renaturalisation initiative carried out in Las Palmeras, a socio-economically marginalised neighbourhood in Córdoba, Spain, within the framework of an H2020 project aimed at enhancing inclusive health and well-being. The renaturalisation initiative involved academics, public administrations, private actors, and residents who collaborated to improve underused public spaces through vegetation planting and environmental redesign. A participatory action research (PAR) framework guided the process (Cornish et al., 2023), with

residents involved in the co-design, co-deployment, and co-management throughout shared care of the new green spaces. The research examined whether and how this intervention influenced residents' well-being, environmental engagement, and perceptions of their neighbourhood. In particular, it considers the possible short-term outcomes for those directly involved in the process, as well as broader effects among the wider community. By focusing on both ecological and social dimensions, the research seeks to contribute to ongoing discussions about the role of participatory approaches in urban greening and environmental equity, and to support new approaches to inclusive policymaking.

2. Methods

2.1. Context of the study area

Córdoba is a city in southern Spain, with a population of approximately 325,000 inhabitants. It has a Mediterranean climate and is characterised by particularly high summer temperatures, making it one of the hottest cities in Spain (AEMET, 2024; Rodríguez-Ballesteros, 2014). The urban landscape includes a range of green spaces, such as peri-urban parks, urban parks, historic gardens, and a riverfront area. Significant social and spatial inequalities also mark the city. Three of its neighbourhoods are among the fifteen most deprived in Spain (Observatorio de Desigualdad de Andalucía, 2023). These include Las Palmeras, Polígono del Guadalquivir, and Moreras. Las Palmeras is a socio-spatially segregated neighbourhood situated on the south-western edge of the city, ranking as the fifth most deprived neighbourhood in the country (Observatorio de Desigualdad de Andalucía, 2023). It covers an area of approximately 114,000 square metres and has a population of around 2212 residents (Ayuntamiento de Córdoba, 2020). The neighbourhood experiences not only physical separation from the rest of the city but also social exclusion, largely driven by its stigmatised reputation. Residents face high rates of unemployment, substance and alcohol misuse, violence, vandalism, illegal activities and limited basic services provided by local authorities. Health-related challenges are also prevalent, with unhealthy lifestyle habits, high obesity rates, and low levels of health, well-being, and perceived mental health. The urban design of the neighbourhood contributes to these issues. Low-quality social houses surround central concrete spaces, exacerbating heat retention and limiting thermal comfort.

2.2. Purpose of the study

In response to the environmental and social challenges faced by Las Palmeras, this study aims to assess the impacts of a participatory-led urban renaturalisation intervention on both ecological and social outcomes within this highly marginalised neighbourhood. The intervention involved researchers, policymakers, local businesses and residents. It established a governance model that combined the institutional and financial capacity of public and private actors with the lived experience and participatory engagement of local residents. Researchers designed a socially responsible public tender using EU funds to renaturalise the area, favouring small, locally-based companies. Public administrations provided permissions and expertise on the best planting conditions. Central to this process was the Participatory Action Research (PAR) approach, which sought to ensure that community members were not merely recipients of green infrastructure but active agents in its design, implementation, and care.

To guide the analysis, the following research questions were developed:

How does participatory urban renaturalisation affect residents' mental well-being, nature engagement, nature relatedness, and perceptions of neighbourhood quality in a socio-economically marginalised community?

How did the participatory process contribute to implementation and early stewardship, and what ecological outcomes (e.g., tree survival and

damage/vandalism during establishment) were observed?

2.3. Participatory Action Research methodology

The research adopted a Participatory Action Research (PAR) approach to promote collaboration among local residents, researchers, and institutional partners (Martinez et al., 2025), involving a co-design, co-deployment, co-management, and co-assessment (co-co-co-co) methodology (Delgado-Serrano et al., 2025). This approach was appropriate due to the social exclusion and low level of institutional trust observed in Las Palmeras. Under these conditions, a traditional top-down intervention was unlikely to succeed without active community participation (Diep et al., 2022; Nobles and Moore., 2024). We operationalised participation through four complementary phases.

The first phase examined health and well-being markers among residents of the neighbourhood. The research team reviewed indicators previously reported in the literature and conducted interviews with residents of Las Palmeras during 2021 to identify the dimensions they associated with health and wellbeing. On this basis, an inclusive, neighbourhood-focused health and well-being assessment framework was developed, including the dimensions and subdimensions relevant to the neighbourhood (Fig. 1). The complete methods and results are reported elsewhere (Mac-Fadden et al., 2024). Once the health and well-being dimensions relevant to the neighbourhood had been identified, a survey and two focus groups discussions were designed to measure all dimensions except economic well-being, as the renaturalisation project does not address this dimension.

All the inhabitants were eligible to participate, and outreach aimed to reach the full neighbourhood through door-to-door contact in key public spaces, announcements via neighbourhood associations, and dissemination through municipal and social media channels in the different activities. A core group of 11–15 neighbourhood volunteers was formed to work with the researchers and companies throughout the whole project and interventions. Volunteers were long-term residents and all of them women except for one man who joined at the end of the project; most were older adults (age range: 50–65), except for two young women in their 20's. Several reported caregiving roles (e.g., grandchildren). Participation varied over time; people left mostly due to competing care/work responsibilities or health constraints, and joined the group due to mouth-to-mouth communication. As such, the core group should be interpreted as a motivated subset of residents rather than a representative cross-section of the neighbourhood. Twelve people

committed to participation for the full duration of the project. In parallel, a public procurement process was launched to select a paid company with EU funds to carry out the renaturalisation process. We selected a local company with roots in the neighbourhood, and together the company and the workers of the project, created 33 co-design unpaid workshops with the neighbours, mostly people from the core-group, but also other participants from the neighbourhood who decided to go. The co-design workshops combined resident preferences (locations, desired uses, and perceived needs) with technical constraints such as species selection, planting season, irrigation requirements, compliance with the municipal guidelines, and ecological suitability assessments led by the company and research team. Co-deployment actions were also based on 15 workshops and on the voluntary participation of all interested neighbours, who worked with the company on the planting process. A new green picnic area was created, and a new corridor next to a stream was built and revegetated. As part of the contract, the company in charge of the renaturalisation provided a gardening course for the volunteers and other people in the neighbourhood. The contracted company delivered a gardening course (open to core volunteers and other interested residents; n = 17 attendees). Participants reported gaining practical planting and maintenance skills, which are essential to engage them in the future co-management of the plants and trees. Finally, co-assessment allowed residents to have an active voice in assessing the renaturalisation process itself, including its priorities, procedures, and perceived fairness, and to have the ability to request adjustments when aspects were not meeting their needs or expectations (Fig. 2).

2.4. Impact Assessment

2.4.1. Ecological outcomes: tree planting and survival

Ecological outcomes were recorded via a tree census in the intervention area. Prior to the renaturalisation, all existing trees in Las Palmeras were mapped, and a baseline count of 279 trees was established (Fig. 3). The planting process was developed following the PAR strategies (see above). Three-hundred and fifty trees and more than 2000 plants and shrubs were planted in the five patios of the neighbourhood, the central square, the corridor and several streets. Planting took place in autumn, aligned with recommended local planting periods for Mediterranean climates. Hence, the trees and plants had around five months to establish themselves before experiencing the extended high temperatures and dry periods of summer (AEMET, 2024). Tree survival was assessed approximately 18 months after planting, when all newly

Fig. 1. Co-created framework for inclusive health and well-being of people in vulnerable neighbourhoods (Mac-Fadden et al., 2024).

Fig. 2. Process of renaturalisation. The photos show the state of the mentioned public places before intervention (Top), during the co-deployment process (Middle), and after refurbishment (Bottom). **A) column** shows the co-creation of the green pathway; **B) column**, the picnic area; **C) column**, one of the patios; and **D) column**, areas of the central square.

Fig. 3. Map of Las Palmeras and photos of the process. A) A map of the city of Córdoba and the neighbourhood of Las Palmeras highlighted with a small red square on the left side; B) zoom of the neighbourhood in a smaller scale; C) Trees in Las Palmeras before intervention and the red circles show the intervention areas; D) Final tree count in Las Palmeras after intervention identify by colour.

planted trees were revisited and classified as either “growing” (alive, with leaves and visible new growth) or “dead/dying” (no leaves, severe

dieback or collapse). Survival rates were calculated for each species and for all trees combined as the proportion of trees classified as growing.

Qualitative observations of visible damage attributable to vandalism were also recorded during the census to contextualise survival patterns.

2.4.2. Study design and quantitative measures

This study received approval from the Human Research Ethics Committee of the University of Córdoba (Reference CEIH-23–35) in 2023. All procedures related to data collection and processing were overseen by a designated data protection officer, ensuring compliance with European data protection regulations (Das, 2018).

We applied a quasi-experimental, repeated cross-sectional design with two survey waves in three socio-economically deprived neighbourhoods in Córdoba: Las Palmeras (intervention) and Moreras and Polígono del Guadalquivir (comparison areas). The three neighbourhoods are recognised by local authorities and national indices as among the most deprived in Spain, with similarly high rates of unemployment, low educational attainment and limited municipal services (Observatorio de Desigualdad de Andalucía, 2023). A baseline survey was conducted in Córdoba between April and June 2023, prior to the start of the renaturalisation activities in Las Palmeras. A follow-up survey was administered between April and May 2025, after completion of the main intervention activities and an initial establishment period for the new green spaces. On average, participants took approximately 20 min to complete the questionnaire, which comprised 37 items (some operationalised as short item batteries using Likert-type response scales); in Las Palmeras, the follow-up survey included three additional intervention-specific questions (40 items in total) (Supplementary material I). Both waves used validated instruments to assess self-perceived well-being, psychological distress, perceived physical health, and nature-related behaviours, and also included items on perceptions of neighbourhood quality and use of green/public spaces. Socio-demographic information, including the neighbourhood of residency, was collected to support the statistical models. Most responses were collected through face-to-face administration in key public spaces, complemented by outreach via social media and local platforms (including neighbourhood associations and municipal websites), following recommended practices for reaching hard-to-survey populations, using social media suggested by Baltar, Brunet., 2012). In both waves, we used non-probability sampling to reach both the general population and individuals from minority or vulnerable backgrounds, consequently, the design is best understood as repeated cross-sectional. Hence, most of the Wave 1 respondents were likely not the same individuals as those in Wave 2, the only confirmed repeat respondents were members of the core group, whose data were analysed separately.

2.4.2.1. Mental health and well-being. Well-being was assessed using standardised and validated measures of self-perceived mental health. These included the WHO-5 Well-Being Index (WHO, 1998), which captures participants' recent experiences of mental well-being. The WHO-5 asks participants to rate five statements, such as "I have felt cheerful and in good spirits" and "I have felt calm and relaxed", according to their experiences over the previous two weeks. Each item is scored from 0 to 5, where 0 indicates "At no time" and 5 indicates "All of the time", resulting in a raw score between 0 and 25. To align with the scale's standard reporting and interpretability conventions, the outcome was converted into a percentage by multiplying the total score by 4. Internal consistency of the WHO-5 was confirmed through Cronbach's alpha ($\alpha = 0.87$, 95% CI: 0.83–0.91). Although the WHO-5 provides valuable insight into self-reported mental states and is widely used in the early detection of depressive symptoms, it remains a subjective measure and may be influenced by momentary mood or response bias.

Psychological distress was assessed using the Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K6) (Kessler et al., 1997). The K6 is a brief screening tool for identifying individuals who may be at risk of serious mental illness. The K6 was selected because it is a brief, widely used screening measure of non-specific psychological distress suitable for community surveys

where respondent burden must be minimised. Moreover, its validity has been demonstrated in several studies, including Prochaska et al., (2012), which support its reliability for measuring clinically significant distress; it has also been used in other studies to assess mental distress and greenness (Delgado-Serrano et al., 2024). Participants rated six statements, such as "I felt nervous" and "I felt hopeless", on a scale from 0 to 4, where 0 meant "Never" and 4 meant "All of the time", based on how they had felt during the past 30 days. The total score ranged from 0 to 24. Internal consistency was confirmed with Cronbach's alpha ($\alpha = 0.89$, 95% CI: 0.87–0.91). As with the WHO-5, this tool relies on self-reporting and may be subject to response bias. Participants also reported their perceived physical health and overall life satisfaction using single items. Self-rated physical health was assessed on a 5-point scale from 1 ("Very poor") to 5 ("Very good"), and life satisfaction on a 5-point scale from 1 ("Very dissatisfied") to 5 ("Very satisfied"). Single items were used to keep the survey short and accessible in a context of respondent fatigue and varying literacy levels. Both variables were used as continuous measures.

2.4.2.2. Nature engagement and nature-relatedness behaviour. To assess residents' nature-relatedness behaviour, the survey included items such as how much time they spent in green areas each day, whether they were aware of the nature around them during the day, whether they exercised in natural environments, and whether they noticed the presence of nature while engaging in those activities. Each item was rated on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 indicated strong disagreement and 5 indicated strong agreement. A 5-point response format was chosen to balance sensitivity with ease of understanding, to allow a neutral midpoint, and to maintain comparability with similar neighbourhood survey research. In addition, the Nature Relatedness Scale (NR-6) was used to measure nature engagement (Nisbet and Zelenski, 2013). For each of six statements, including "My ideal holiday spot would be a remote and natural location", participants selected a response from 1 ("Strongly disagree") to 5 ("Strongly agree"). Responses to the six NR-6 items were average to create a total score ranging from 1 to 5, with higher values indicating a stronger nature-relatedness. The internal consistency of the NR-6 was good ($\alpha = 0.88$, 95% CI: 0.86–0.89).

2.4.2.3. Neighbourhood perception and intervention-specific questions. Perceptions of neighbourhood and public space were assessed using items on perceived change in neighbourhood image, sense of community, safety in green and public areas, relationships with neighbours, and presence of public activities. Responses were rated on a 5-point scale from 1 ("No change") to 5 ("Strong positive change") and treated as continuous variables. Moreover, in the follow-up survey in Las Palmeras, three additional items were included to capture perceptions specific to the implemented interventions: perceived overall impact of the new green spaces on the neighbourhood (1 = very negative, 5 = very positive), frequency of social interactions since the renaturalisation (1 = never, 4 = very often), and change in use of public spaces (1 = much less than before, 5 = much more than before).

Finally, the members of the core group were tracked separately through an anonymised dataset to examine whether their reported outcomes differed from those of other residents in Las Palmeras. While their responses helped interpret the qualitative findings, they were not analysed as a separate sample in the quantitative results because of the small group size, which included only eleven women and one man; these were the volunteers of the core group who agreed to participate in the survey and focus group discussions.

2.4.3. Statistical analysis

For the preliminary analysis, to avoid issues related to assumption violations, randomisation tests were used instead of the *t*-test, since randomisation methods provide valid inference without normality assumptions (Manly, 2018). For variables where a significant association

was identified, generalised linear models (GLMs) were then developed. Before running the models, sociodemographic variables were examined to ensure model stability. The category "non-binary" for gender was excluded because only a limited number of respondents identified as such across all neighbourhoods. Potential associations among socio-demographic predictors were tested using chi-squared tests for categorical variables and randomisation tests for numerical variables, to reduce inflated variance. A correlation was observed between "highest level of education achieved" and "employment status". Given the established relationship between employment status and both well-being and psychological distress (Bonanomi and Rosina, 2022), the variable "employment status" was used in the final models. In all GLMs, the main predictor of interest was the interaction between neighbourhood (Las Palmeras, Polígono del Guadalquivir, and Moreras) and survey wave (pre-intervention versus post-intervention). Models were adjusted for gender, age, and employment status. To improve the reliability of the estimates and address potential heteroskedasticity, robust standard errors were applied. To account for multiple comparisons across correlated outcomes, we controlled the false discovery rate using the Benjamini–Hochberg procedure with a false discovery rate set at 0.05 (Benjamini and Hochberg, 1995).

For outcomes where preliminary analyses suggested differences over time or between neighbourhoods, we fitted generalised linear models (GLMs) to assess the effect of the intervention. For continuous outcomes (WHO-5, K6, NR-6, self-rated health, life satisfaction, time in nature, exercising in green areas, awareness of nature and neighbourhood image), we used GLMs with an identity link and Gaussian family. For Likert-type items, we treated the scores as approximately continuous, which is common practice in similar survey-based studies (Donovan et al., 2013; Hunter et al., 2019), and verified that residuals did not show major deviations from normality.

To control for multiple comparisons across the set of social and health-related outcomes, we applied the Benjamini–Hochberg procedure with a false discovery rate of 0.05. Unless otherwise stated, β coefficients reported in the results represent adjusted differences in the outcome score between pre- and post-intervention in Las Palmeras relative to the comparison neighbourhoods. Surveys completed by members of the core volunteer group were not included in the main quantitative analysis due to the small sample size ($n = 12$) and their non-representative socio-demographic profile (predominantly women and older adults). As a robustness check, we additionally ran bootstrap models comparing the women volunteers ($n = 11$) with women of similar age in Las Palmeras, Moreras, and Polígono de Guadalquivir, and used these results to assess whether observed patterns were consistent with the themes emerging from the focus group discussions (see 2.5). All analyses were conducted using R software (R Core Team., 2025).

2.5. Focus group discussions

To explore residents' perspectives on the intervention and its perceived impacts, we conducted two focus group discussions with members of the core group. The first took place shortly after the main planting activities, and the second approximately 18 months later, to reflect on the overall process and its outcomes. All participants gave written informed consent. Sessions were audio-recorded and transcribed by an independent member of the research team (software-based transcription was not possible due to the language used by participants and several people speaking at once), with all personal identifiers removed. A semi-structured guide was used to prompt discussion around perceived changes in personal well-being, health-related behaviours, social relations, neighbourhood atmosphere, and attitudes towards public space and the new vegetation.

3. Results

3.1. Tree planting and survival rate

Before starting the planting process, a total of 279 trees existed in the neighbourhood; the project planted 350 trees, which implied an increase of 117.85% in tree presence in the neighbourhood. The project also planted around 2000 shrubs, but the percentage of increase in greenness cannot be assessed due to the lack of an initial count of small plants. The intervention was distributed across multiple common spaces within Las Palmeras, including public patios, the central square, and streets across the neighbourhood. The only site-specific interventions were the picnic area and the corridor, which may have been less accessible for some older residents living farther away; however, overall, the renaturalisation was broadly and relatively evenly distributed across the neighbourhood. Two years after planting, overall survival across the intervention area was approximately 82%, with high survival in heat-tolerant species such as *Jacaranda mimosifolia* (97%) and *Tipuana tipu* (95%), and lower survival in *Populus alba* (40%) and *Populus nigra* (57%) (Table 1). However, the significant share of losses among *Populus* trees was linked to an outbreak of *Vespa velutina*, which stripped bark and led to secondary infections, resulting in the loss of 16 trees. Only two trees have been lost due to human actions (vandalism) after two years. Although we lack scientific evidence for direct comparison in Mediterranean environments, we believe that the survival rate is higher than usual because neighbours tend to care for the trees, especially during the extremely hot last two summers. Evidence of the importance of stewardship of trees during their first years has been highlighted in the literature (Roman et al., 2015).

3.2. Sociodemographics

Table 2 presents the sociodemographic characteristics of the two surveys. Women were overrepresented in both survey waves and in all neighbourhoods, although the proportion decreased slightly between baseline and follow-up. The average age was around 40 years in Las Palmeras and mid-40s in the comparison neighbourhoods in both waves. Educational attainment remained lower in Las Palmeras, where very few respondents reported a university degree, while around one-third of respondents in the comparison areas had higher education. Unemployment was common in all three neighbourhoods, but consistently higher in Las Palmeras.

3.3. Questionnaires outcomes

After adjustment for gender, age, and employment status, no statistically significant changes were detected in WHO-5, K6, self-rated health, or life satisfaction between baseline and follow-up in any of

Table 1
Survival rate of trees by species. The colour before the name of the species matches the colour in Fig. 2. *Ulmus resista* has no colour because all trees planted died.

	Death/ or dying	Growing	Total	Percentage of survival
<i>fx 1 Frixinus</i>	8	2	10	20%
<i>fx 2 Celtis australis</i>	11	33	44	75%
<i>Ulmus resista</i>	7	0	7	0%
<i>fx 3 Citrus limon</i>	3	10	13	77%
<i>fx 4 Citrus aurantium</i>	2	18	20	90%
<i>fx 5 Tipuana tipu</i>	4	86	90	95%
<i>fx 6 Jacaranda mimosifolia</i>	3	103	106	97%
<i>fx 7 Grevillea robusta</i>	7	19	26	73%
<i>fx 8 Populus nigra</i>	6	8	14	57%
<i>fx 9 Populus alba</i>	12	8	20	40%
Total	63	287	350	82%

Table 2

Table of the sociodemographic characteristics between the two surveys, on the left the survey before intervention and on the right the survey after the renaturalisation process.

	Pre- survey		Post - survey	
	Mar-Pol, N = 133 ^a	Palmeras, N = 112 ^a	Mar-Pol, N = 106 ^a	Palmeras, N = 96 ^a
Gender				
Female	83 (62%) ^a	73 (65%) ^a	58 (55%) ^a	51 (55%) ^a
Male	50 (38%)	39 (35%)	46 (43%)	40 (43%)
Prefer not to say or other	0 (0%)	1 (0.1%)	2 (1.9%)	2 (2.2%)
Age				
	47 (± 17) ^b	40 (± 17) ^b	46 (± 16) ^b	39 (± 15) ^b
Education				
University degree or higher	34 (25.5%)	2 (1.8%)	31 (29%)	3 (3.2%)
Higher level of vocational training	26 (20%)	3 (2.6%)	16 (15%)	7 (7.5%)
Intermediate level of vocational training	6 (4.5%)	3 (2.6%)	14 (13%)	26 (28%)
No education	11 (8.3%)	29 (26%)	18 (17%)	15 (16%)
Primary or secondary education	56 (42%)	75 (67%)	27 (25%)	42 (45%)
Working status				
Full-time job	34 (26%)	9 (6.9%)	22 (21%)	16 (17%)
Other	10 (7.5%)	12 (11%)	15 (14%)	16 (17%)
Part-time job	9 (6.8%)	13 (12%)	12 (11%)	9 (9.7%)
Retired	21 (16%)	10 (8.7%)	18 (17%)	4 (4.3%)
Self-employed or freelance	14 (11%)	2 (1.8%)	6 (5.7%)	3 (3.2%)
Unemployed	45 (34%)	66 (59%)	33 (31%)	45 (48%)

^a Total number of participants (n) and equivalent percentage in the sample (%) for categorical data;

^b Mean of the sample and standard deviation (sd)

the neighbourhoods, after controlling for multiple comparisons.

In contrast, several indicators of nature engagement showed improvements in Las Palmeras relative to the comparison neighbourhoods. The NR-6 total score increased by an adjusted mean of 0.9 points (95% CI: 0.4, 1.3; corrected $p < 0.001$). Time spent in natural environments during the day ($\beta = 0.69$; 95% CI: 0.13, 1.2; corrected $p = 0.005$), exercising in green areas ($\beta = 1.3$; 95% CI: 0.73, 2; corrected $p < 0.001$), and awareness of nature during such activities ($\beta = 1.4$; 95% CI: 0.75, 2.1; corrected $p < 0.001$) also increased in Las Palmeras, while no comparable changes were observed in the comparison areas.

Perceptions of neighbourhood image improved in Las Palmeras relative to the other neighbourhoods ($\beta = 1.3$; SE = 0.2; 95% CI: 0.53, 2.0; corrected $p = 0.004$). Other social indicators, including perceived safety, sense of community and relationships with neighbours, did not show statistically significant changes after correction for multiple testing.

Responses to three additional questions asked exclusively in Las Palmeras suggested that residents generally viewed the intervention positively. When asked, "In what way do you think the interventions have affected the neighbourhood?", responses were mixed. Four respondents considered the impact "extremely negative", and another four described it as "somewhat negative". Twenty-six selected a neutral response, while 27 reported the changes as "somewhat positive", and 32 described them as "extremely positive". While we did not systematically collect qualitative explanations from survey respondents, negative views may reflect concerns about other preferences for other types of investments. Future work should capture reasons for critical responses through short follow-up questions or interviews. Nevertheless, overall, these results point to a generally favourable view of the intervention, although a proportion of respondents remained neutral or critical.

The second question asked, "Since the renaturalisation, how often do you socialise with others?" Ten respondents reported "never", and 19 answered "almost never". Eighteen said they socialised "sometimes", while 46 indicated they did so "often". This distribution suggests that for an important part of the respondents, the new green areas have created new places for socialisation, even if for others, the new places have not changed their socialisation patterns.

The third question focused on changes in the use of public spaces. Participants were asked, "Since the renaturalisation, do you use public spaces more?" Five respondents indicated that they used such spaces "way less than before", and five chose "somewhat less than before".

Twenty-seven gave a neutral response, while another 27 said they used public space "somewhat more than before". The largest group, 29 respondents, stated that they used public areas "way more than before". These responses suggest a general increase in the use of public spaces, although nearly one-third of participants either did not report a change or indicated a reduction in use.

3.4. Focus group discussions results

Participants in both sessions described the project as a source of positive change within the neighbourhood, particularly regarding the condition and use of public spaces. They noted improvements in the overall appearance of the area, including the central square and patios, newly planted streets, and the pedestrian zone near the stream. These changes were seen to have contributed to a more pleasant and usable environment.

Beyond physical improvements, many participants reported increased contact with neighbours and a greater sense of connection to the local environment. Several individuals stated that involvement in the project had created opportunities to engage with others and take part in shared activities, which they had rarely experienced previously. Participants linked this shift to the participatory nature of the intervention, which allowed them to be active members in decisions about design and maintenance. Some indicated that this had led to a greater willingness to care for public spaces and to support their preservation over time.

A number of residents described a perceived improvement in emotional well-being. They referred to feelings of pride, satisfaction, and renewed interest in their surroundings, which they attributed to their involvement in the project. These reflections correspond with changes in individual survey data collected from members of the core group, who reported increases in their WHO-5 Well-Being Index from 16.2 to 19.9 and reductions in Kessler Psychological Distress (K6) scores from 10.3 to 7.8. The mean Nature Relatedness score (NR-6) also increased from 2.7 to 3.54, suggesting a stronger reported connection to natural environments.

Participants commented on the improved social atmosphere in the neighbourhood and referred to the emergence of new relationships and informal cooperation. For instance, several individuals said they had begun watering plants together, helped in maintaining shared areas, or organised group activities. Perceived improvements in trust and mutual

respect were mentioned as outcomes of the collaborative work. Quantitative responses supported these impressions: scores for perceived neighbour relations increased from 3.6 to 4.08, while the presence of public activities improved from 2.0 to 3.2.

The most notable change appeared in perceptions of the neighbourhood's image. The average score for this item rose from 1.7 to 4.33 among core group members, reflecting a shift in their evaluation of their surroundings. Participants interpreted this change not only as a response to the physical upgrades but also as a result of their involvement in bringing them about. Many said the project made them feel that their efforts had produced visible outcomes and that this sense of contribution had altered their perception of the area.

Although many reflections were positive, participants also acknowledged that some challenges remained. These included limited economic opportunities, a lack of municipal services, neglect of public space care, and continued social exclusion. While participants expressed satisfaction with the environmental improvements, they did not believe these changes could resolve wider structural problems without further public investment and institutional support.

4. Discussion

This study examined a participatory renaturalisation project in a socioeconomically marginalised neighbourhood, using a quasi-experimental design to compare changes in Las Palmeras with those in two similar areas. The intervention combined co-design, co-deployment, co-management through early maintenance and co-assessment of the process of renaturalisation using a Participatory Action Research approach. The main findings showed improvements in neighbourhood image among participants and a clearer though narrower improvement in the wider Las Palmeras sample, higher nature-relatedness and more frequent contact with local green space in the intervention area, and high tree survival after 18 months, with very limited vandalism. Population-wide health indicators did not change in a clear way over the study window. Taken together, the results suggest that immediate social and stewardship outcomes appear first, while direct ecosystem services from trees, such as shade and heat reduction, will require time to develop as trees mature.

With respect to the first research question, the project appears to have influenced mental well-being and perceptions of neighbourhood quality in two related but distinct ways. Among the core group that took part in the PAR process, and as shown by the qualitative focus group discussions and the survey, respondents reported better perceived well-being, stronger ties with neighbours and a marked improvement in neighbourhood image. This pattern is consistent with work that links direct participation in urban greening to agency, place attachment and social connection, and with evidence that contributing to visible change can provide psychosocial value (Jennings and Bamkole, 2019; Raymond et al., 2017). The largest gains were in perceived neighbourhood image, which participants linked to the physical upgrades and to their own role in making them, in line with studies of resident involvement and local pride after visible improvements (Kondo et al., 2018; Larson et al., 2016). In contrast, population-wide health indicators for Las Palmeras did not clearly shift during the study period, aligning with research suggesting that broader health effects usually require longer exposure and supportive social policy (Bratman et al., 2019; Rigolon et al., 2021). The introduction noted that ecosystem services such as measurable cooling, shading and air quality regulation tend to appear after trees have grown. The present results support that hypothesis, as our outcomes show that social and emotional benefits appeared by the time we conducted the follow-up survey, whereas other ecosystem benefits will likely require more time (Li et al., 2024). Moreover, we believed that it is plausible that the core group did not show large changes in nature related behaviours because many members were older or faced physical constraints, and their primary motivation lay in improving the shared environment for the benefit of others (mainly their

descendants) rather than for their own use at that time, as state by three women in the group saying that they were doing all the work for their grandchildren. Although older residents were not explicitly targeted, it appears they were more available for daytime workshops and expressed strong motivations linked to caregiving and neighbourhood legacy. We believed that identifying such residents, not only old people, but also motivated people, who act as conveners and caretakers, may be important when working in communities with limited trust in institutions.

About the second research question, the participatory greening approach appears to have influenced nature engagement and nature-related behaviours among the wider community. Adjusted models for non-participant neighbours of Las Palmeras indicated higher nature-relatedness, more time outdoors, more exercise in green areas and greater attentiveness to nature during activity, with no comparable change in the comparison areas. These changes are consistent with studies showing that nearby and decent quality green space can change everyday behaviour when baseline access is limited (Donovan et al., 2013; R. F. Hunter et al., 2019). The findings suggest that, for many residents, the availability of a usable, proximate green area is sufficient to prompt use, regardless of formal participation in planning or planting. In this sense, our governance model worked through two channels. The PAR process helped a small number of residents develop ownership, confidence and informal oversight, and through casual conversation with the rest of the neighbours, they might have convinced others to reduce vandalism and discourage damage. These results are in line with evidence suggesting that resident participation in the management and improvement of local environments may increase feelings of responsibility and place identification, which in turn can reduce vandalism and improve everyday care of public spaces (Lindgren and Castell, 2008; Mohr-Stockinger et al., 2023). At the same time, institutional delivery of visible, well-maintained improvements provided conditions for the wider public to visit and spend time in nature without additional incentives. Focus group accounts of shared watering and light maintenance indicate that these channels succeeded, as regular presence in public space can serve as casual guardianship and potentially reduce opportunities for damage, as discussed in the introduction with reference to collective efficacy and routine activity explanations deficits (Ceccato and Haining, 2005; Dede et al., 2025; Keizer et al., 2008).

Ecological performance during tree establishment supports this reading. Eighteen months later, overall survival was 82 per cent despite prolonged high temperatures. Survival was high for heat-tolerant species and lower for less suitable taxa, and only two trees were vandalised. These outcomes are consistent with the view that, in poorer and segregated neighbourhoods where damage to public goods may be more common, visible participation, early training and timely maintenance can help avert damage and secure the establishment phase (Roman et al., 2015). Species choice, planting season and irrigation needs steered by researchers and administrations, together with neighbour care, appear to have supported survival during the first year. The greater thermal and ecological benefits will depend on sustained care over several years, which strengthens the case that projects in such settings should prioritise stewardship functions from the outset. By protecting young plantings before canopy formation, these practices make it more likely that trees will reach sizes that provide shade, reduce heat, and support biodiversity (Li et al., 2024; Mohr-Stockinger et al., 2023; Roman et al., 2015).

The combined pattern of results mirrors findings from other disadvantaged urban contexts. Local environmental improvements may produce valued outcomes in image and engagement, yet they do not address structural disadvantages related to unemployment, access to services and exclusion in the short term (Rigolon and Németh, 2020; Wolch et al., 2014a). The present study adds that early social outcomes, such as appropriation, pride, and everyday presence in public space, can limit vandalism and appear to protect new plantings, while the direct ecosystem services accumulate more slowly. In this light, the

participatory greening process that pairs institutional capacity with a participatory core might be well-suited to neighbourhoods where stewardship needs to be demonstrated quickly. The broader population uses nearby green areas when they exist and are of adequate quality, while a small group of resident caretakers helps keep those places in use and in good condition, which in turn appears to improve their mental well-being along the process. If institutions maintain support (e.g. irrigation/maintenance funding or replacement of dead trees) and residents continue to feel ownership (e.g. co-monitoring survival of trees and report any issues or cleaning sessions of common areas), the intervention is more likely to progress to the stage at which trees provide measurable cooling, shade, and other ecosystem services.

5. Limitations

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting the findings of this study. First, the sample size in both survey waves was relatively small. This may have reduced the statistical power of the analyses and limited the ability to detect more subtle changes over time. In addition, both survey waves relied on non-probability sampling, and the target and achieved sample sizes differed between baseline and follow-up and across neighbourhoods. The baseline and follow-up samples should therefore be understood as independent cross-sections rather than a longitudinal sample, and changes over time may partly reflect differences in who agreed to participate in each wave. It is also likely that the samples over-represent residents who were more accessible or more willing to engage with the project, which may bias estimates of absolute levels of health and well-being, although relative comparisons between neighbourhoods remain informative. Although the findings indicate some differences between pre- and post-intervention conditions, these results should be interpreted with caution due to the variability in response rates and potential sampling bias.

Second, the study relied primarily on self-reported data for both health and behavioural outcomes. While validated instruments such as the WHO-5 and K6 were used, self-reported measures remain subject to individual interpretation and response bias. Participants' answers may have been influenced by temporary mood, social desirability, or recall limitations. This is particularly relevant in the context of subjective indicators such as well-being, neighbourhood perception, and connection to nature.

Third, the intervention was implemented in a single neighbourhood and was associated with an R&I project that provided funds, researchers, and facilitators to mobilise local residents over a long period. The results may not be generalisable to other urban areas with different social, cultural, or institutional contexts. While the findings provide insight into how participatory greening may influence perceptions and behaviours in a marginalised setting, further research is needed to examine whether similar approaches would produce comparable outcomes elsewhere.

Fourth, it remains difficult to assess the full range of benefits associated with renaturalisation at this stage, given that most trees and shrubs are still in the early stages of growth. Many of the ecological and microclimatic effects of increased vegetation are likely to become more apparent over a longer period, once tree canopy cover expands and root systems mature. In this sense, the short-term impacts identified in this study may reflect the social and psychological effects of participation in the process, rather than the direct ecological benefits of reforestation. Future evaluations conducted after several growing seasons may provide a more complete picture of the intervention's outcomes. Finally, the duration of the post-intervention follow-up was relatively short. While the study captured changes 18 months after the implementation of the renaturalisation activities, some ecological and social outcomes may take longer to emerge. The limited timeframe also restricted the assessment of long-term maintenance, seasonal variation, and potential

changes in use patterns over time.

Finally, we did not measure individual-level exposure to the intervention (e.g., awareness, receipt of information, participation/volunteering, or frequency of contact with the new sites). This choice was made to minimise respondent burden and maintain a short, accessible questionnaire in a hard-to-survey context, and because anonymity constraints limited the collection of location- or participation-identifying information. As a result, variation in exposure may have contributed to heterogeneity in perceived impacts.

6. Conclusions

This study examined a participatory urban renaturalisation initiative in a marginalised neighbourhood. The project combined a hybrid governance model, in which public administrations and researchers provided technical and financial support, with a Participatory Action Research approach that gave a group of residents a central role in co-design, co-deployment, co-management and co-assessment. Taken together, the study's findings suggest that participatory renaturalisation in marginalised environments could contribute to more liveable and equitable neighbourhoods, although the effects remain partial and depend on broader conditions.

The results support several conclusions for policy and practice. First, local participation appears important not as an accessory element but as a central component that may build trust and neighbourhood pride, particularly where residents have experienced institutional neglect. Second, co-design processes that respect residents' preferences while remaining consistent with technical and legal constraints may create green spaces that people recognise as their own, thereby ensuring care and supporting public authorities' maintenance activities. Third, basic training in planting and care for interested residents may increase the likelihood that new vegetation survives the establishment phase and, in some cases, may open opportunities for skills development. Fourth, small-scale projects of this kind appear to require a connection with wider urban strategies on spatial inequality, public health and climate adaptation, so that they do not remain isolated or symbolic interventions. Finally, the short follow-up period and the early stage of tree growth mean that many ecological and health benefits are likely to emerge in the future, which underlines the need for long-term monitoring of social and biophysical outcomes. Future research in other cities and neighbourhoods could assess the transferability of this hybrid and participatory model and examine the conditions under which community greening may contribute to lasting improvements in environmental justice and population health.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Catalina Cruz-Piedrahita: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Francisco Javier Martinez-Carranza:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Maria Mar Delgado-Serrano:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Investigation.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.ufug.2026.129439](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2026.129439).

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